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Evaluation of Real-Life LoRaWAN Localization: Accuracy Dependencies Analysis Based on Outdoor Measurement Datasets

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Abstract—Modern outdoor localization is commonly dependent on various Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSSs). On the other hand, they are known to be power-hungry and not suitable for resource-constrained devices currently flooding the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). Nonetheless, some of those devices may be equipped with Low-Power Wide-Area Network (LPWAN) communication chip that could be utilized for positioning. Current work examines two outdoor datasets collected using LoRaWAN in Brno, Czech Republic, to assess the possibility of applying technology for localization solutions for industrial outdoor scenarios. The main localization approach applied in this work is k-NN fingerprinting. For the first dataset gathered over the whole city, the minimal mean localization error turned out to be not stable, while accuracy for the second one covering a small rectangular area 8.5 x 70 m is 6.42 m that sounds promising in terms of LoRaWAN-based localization. Moreover, by analyzing data collected in two independent measurements campaigns, this work provides some derivations related to the accuracy dependencies on parameters of the measurement campaign (gateways (GWs), coverage area, the average distance between measurement points). It makes a step towards comparing the results of published papers in this area obtained for different datasets.

Index Terms—positioning, measurements, outdoors, dataset, localization, LoRaWAN, LoRa

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) is the part of the Internet of Things (IoT) concept, which focuses on the connected smart objects (sensors, wearables, actuators, etc.), facilitating information management and providing a real-time picture of work processes in an industrial environment to increase operational efficiency and level of work safety [1]. During COVID-19, many enterprises were forced to reduce capacity or close, which negatively affected the growth of the IIoT market but did not stop it: in 2021-2025, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is expected to reach 33% [2] especially boosted by the contact-tracing usecases [3]. Among the key factors that

boost the market's growth are the fast digitalization of enterprises within Industry 4.0 and the related rising level of adoption of various IIoT devices due to their reliability and wide functionality [4].

Specifically, one of the main functions of industrial IIoT *wearable* devices is the precise localization of workers/equipment, which is a necessary parameter in the industrial scenario since the known position of the objects allows a more effective redistribution of workforce and helps prevent collisions and unauthorized access to the machinery and dangerous worksites, plan evacuations in emergency case. Currently, the most adopted solutions for localization are Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) outdoors, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), IEEE 802.11 (a.k.a., Wi-Fi), and Ultra-wideband (UWB) indoors [5], [6].

Not surprisingly, the majority of existing localization solutions have major drawbacks, most of which come from a trade-off between accuracy, power consumption, and availability in terms of cost, presence on the market, and compatibility with wearables [7]. In addition, there is still no feasible proven solution for seamless localization, while industrial scenarios often include both indoors and outdoors. Thus, the question of appropriate localization solutions for wearable devices remains an open research gap.

Long-Range Wide-Area Network (LoRaWAN) is a non-cellular Low-Power WAN (LPWAN) solution that found a place among leading IoT communication technologies of today due to low-cost deployment, direct connection to the cloud, the possibility to identify positions and to apply it outdoor and indoor [8], [9]. In turn, LoRaWAN, developed by the LoRa Alliance, stands for the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer protocol, which leverages and includes the physical LoRa modulation of Semtech. LoRa frequency bands are located in the sub-GHz band, giving it more penetration ability than Wi-Fi and Bluetooth, which operate

Fig. 1: The conceptual architecture of the fingerprinting dataset collection system

in GHz bands. Those factors make LoRaWAN a perspective communication solution for the industrial scenario when we do not need high throughput, but rather the system's low cost and high reliability. While LoRaWAN-based localization may provide a low-cost, low-power, wide-range solution, ensuring appropriate positioning accuracy for IIoT. Unfortunately, current literature reports that the accuracy of localization based on LoRaWAN is quite low.

The purpose of this work is to assess the LoRaWAN-based outdoor localization accuracy based on the two datasets collected in Brno, Czech Republic (see Figure 1). Based on the comparison, this work brings some derivations on the dependency of the accuracy on different factors (number of reference gateway nodes (GWs), the area covered, spacing between the measurement points (MPs)). Also, it draws a preliminary conclusion about the prospects for the development of LoRaWAN technology to apply as a complex solution for communication and localization in the area of industrial wearable devices.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II highlights key related works; Section III presents the description and analysis of the collected datasets; Section IV provides the estimated position accuracy and comparison; Section V discusses the results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and sets the directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

As of today, the research community is still lacking LoRaWAN datasets focused on localization, and there are only a few available to the public [10], [11], [12]. The biggest and the most similar in terms of content to the datasets used in this work is the fingerprinting dataset

in [12] collected during three months in Antwerp with postal cars carrying transceivers. It contains data reported by 68 GWs scattered in the city and real Global Positioning System (GPS) locations from which transceivers sent uplink messages. The authors obtained a mean error of 398.4 m using the k -nearest neighbors algorithm (k -NN) with $k = 11$ nearest GWs.

Regarding the localization methods, some works investigate the credibility of the LoRaWAN solution for an outdoor localization using Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA), Time of Arrival (ToA), Angle of Arrival (AoA) [13], [14], [15]. However, all these methods require additional equipment, unlike the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) approach, where the localization is calculated based on the attenuation that the signal suffers while passing from the end node to the GW. Thus, mainly the RSSI-based method is applied and described in the literature, although the positioning results significantly suffer in the NLOS case.

Other works exploit various Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms [16], such as Support Vector Regression (SVM) [17], Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [18] to increase the accuracy of LoRa-based localization. For example, the authors of [19] present 6 RSSI localization algorithms that aimed at a reduction of the non-Gaussian noise by identifying "good/bad" GWs during the position estimation.

Papers published so far focus on achieving better localization accuracy on the stage of the algorithm. At the same time, they usually use datasets that could be very different in terms of data collection conditions. That is why it might be quite challenging to compare the results and come up with certain accuracy values for LoRaWAN-based localization. This paper puts this problem in the spotlight. Unlike other works, along with estimating the mean localization error for two outdoor datasets, it highlights the manipulation with the localization accuracy not during the data processing, but before collecting it, reviewing different aspects of measurement campaign within k -NN fingerprinting approach.

III. DATASETS DESCRIPTION

This section deals with the specifics of the two measurement campaigns conducted in Brno, Czech Republic. It describes the areas, collection processes, structures, and datasets' nature.

A. The dataset collected from public stops throughout the city (Dataset №1)

The collection process and data structure of this measurement campaign are described in detail in [20]. During 2 days from each of 96 locations associated with the stops of public transport were sent 5 uplink messages (packets) using Field Test Device (FTD) LoRaWAN 868 [21] with a GPS receiver onboard. Each packet potentially was

supposed to be received by 22 GWs that are scattered in (16 GWs) and near (6 GWs) Brno, see Figure 2.

Fig. 2: MPs and location of the gateways (dataset №1)

Fig. 3: Distribution of RSSI values (Dataset №1)

Figure 3 shows the distribution of all received RSSI values. The average value of the signal is -106 dBm, which indicates the scatter-rich environment. On average, each uplink message was received by 4 (4.46) GWs out of 22.

To conclude, this dataset is quite noisy and sparse. 21.7% of uplink messages were received by less than 3 GWs, which excludes the possibility of assessing the position using the trilateration method. The investigated territory is a high-density urban area. Consequently, there is a case of an NLOS scenario when the signal propagates, undergoing multipath effects. Moreover, talking about localization, it should be mentioned that the investigated area is covered with a small number of measurement points, which were taken in the places of public transport stops. Consequently, the MPs are distributed not evenly over the considered

area, and the walk time between two adjacent points is in 1 to 5 minutes of walk: the distance varies between $72m - 1.34km$, on average about $0.50km$. Estimating the localization accuracy for this data set is of interest for studying LoRaWAN as a localization solution and for identifying the dependence of localization accuracy on the conditions of the measurement campaign. However, considering all the factors, the anticipated localization accuracy is very low, approximately hundreds of meters or kilometers.

B. The dataset collected in a small area with pre-deployed GWs (Dataset №2)

This dataset was collected in the area of the Brno University of Technology (BUT) during two days: 7 GWs were pre-deployed on the 5th floor in the building, and MPs were located within the rectangular $8.5m \times 70m$ area in the aboveground parking lot in front of the building (see Figure 5). It was decided to create a separate Cartesian coordinate system where the measurement points and locations of the GWs are strictly defined to exclude the complications with the identification of real positions (see Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Coordinate system: parking lot with GWs

The data could be split into two parts, each part took one day. The first part, Dataset 2.1 in Figure 4, contains 45 MPs arranged in 3 rows of 15 MPs each. The spacing between MPs in each row is $5m$, spacing between rows is $2.5m$. Consequently, spacing between MPs is $3.54m$. The second part, Dataset 2.2, contains 45 MPs in line with the more

Fig. 5: The environment of the second experiment: BUT building and parking lot

dense spacing: $2.5m$. During the measurement campaign, 3 UL messages were sent using FTD from each MP on the parking lot to be received by 7 GWs distributed on the 5th floor of the office building. The time interval between messages lies within 20-60 s.

Figure 6 shows the distribution of RSSI values obtained during this experiment (the analysis was conducted for both, Dataset 2.1 and 2.2); the average value is -97.9 dBm. In this case, each message was received at an average of 6 (5.81) GWs out of 7.

Fig. 6: Distribution of RSSI values (Dataset №2)

IV. INVESTIGATION ON LOCALIZATION ACCURACY

This section considers the localization accuracy obtained for two described datasets and investigates its dependency on different factors such as area and number of GWs.

The first essential step before localization is the data preparation:

- readings were exported from the LoRa server in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format;
- both datasets were resorted and reduced to the form shown in Figure 7;
- out-of-range levels of RSSI were set to values lower than the receiver sensitivity (-140 dBm);
- for k -NN, a redundancy caused by multiple messages per MP (5 – for the Dataset №1, 3 – Dataset №2) that entails overfitting of the model was removed from the data by selecting for each location just one reading with the highest average level of RSSI. Then the order of readings were randomized to avoid overfitting the ML model, and divided into training and test sets in the standard proportion of 80 to 20%, respectively. In both cases k -NN distance matrices were calculated in Euclidean space.

For the Dataset №1, we started from the basic methods related to the GWs position to roughly estimate the accuracy, namely, trilateration and the Weighted Centroid Algorithm (WCA). In the case of trilateration, the distance-power gradient was determined by the characteristics of the signal propagation medium and for Dataset №1 was set as 4 (shaded urban scenario) [22].

Fig. 7: Resorted data

After receiving the first results, we applied the basic machine learning method, k -NN, for more precise localization.

A. Dataset №1

The mean errors for the dataset gathered from public stops throughout Brno are presented in Table I.

TABLE I: Mean Errors (Dataset №1)

Localization approach	Mean Error (m)
Trilateration	12022
WCA	3781
k -NN ($k = 1$)	1047
k -NN ($k = 2$)	1281
k -NN ($k = 3$)	1352
k -NN ($k = 4$)	1462
k -NN ($k = 5$)	1494
k -NN ($k = 6$)	1524
k -NN ($k = 11$)	1694

TABLE II: Mean Errors (Dataset №2)

Parameters	Mean Error (m)				
	2.1	2.2		2.1 (RL)	2.2 (RL)
Case	a	b	c	d	e
MPs	45	45	23	15	30
Spacing, m	3.54	2.5	5	5	2.5
k -NN ($k = 1$)	6.56	8.49	10.89	9.22	6.85
k -NN ($k = 2$)	6.56	8.49	10.89	9.22	6.85
k -NN ($k = 3$)	6.42	7.48	12.19	12.34	5.72
k -NN ($k = 4$)	7.33	9.81	14.30	10.34	6.56
k -NN ($k = 5$)	8.38	9.79	15.94	10.85	5.53
k -NN ($k = 6$)	7.68	9.38	16.71	13.48	5.07

The minimal mean localization error was observed in the case of k -NN with $k = 2$. Such accuracy is anticipated, however, obviously, not sufficient for localization purposes: it is appropriate to identify the trajectory of a bus along the chosen streets. In addition to what was said above, such large errors could also be attributed to the number and

distribution of LoRaWAN GWs: this number is sufficient to create a wireless network but not enough to provide acceptable accuracy in the city environment.

Considering that this dataset was not initially gathered for localization purposes, it was decided to conduct another measurement campaign for outdoor LoRaWAN-based localization.

B. Dataset №2

Since the methods based on the GWs' positions, trilateration and WCA, gave low localization accuracy and can be used just for the rough estimation of the position, we decided to focus on k -NN algorithm with $k = 2, \dots, 6$. The mean errors for the datasets collected in front of the Brno University of Technology are presented in Table II, where DS is dataset and RL – red line, line of MPs specified in Figure 4.

In this case, the smallest error is observed for $k = 3$ nearest neighbors. Despite the different nature of the measurement campaign, represented particularly by a smaller area, more dense and even spacing of the MPs, higher amount of pre-deployed GWs, the obtained precision is still relatively low.

The reason could lay in the nature of the dataset. Let us investigate the distribution of the signal levels for several MPs of the dataset № 2.2. It was decided to take two neighbor MPs (№ 25 and №26) and two MPs from the different sides of the measurement area (№5 and №45) for comparison, see Figure 8. The results of the comparison are represented in Figure 9.

Fig. 8: MC in BUT: investigation of the signal levels for several MPs

Based on Figure 9, we can conclude that the average signal strength for the MP №45 that is closer to the GWs

Fig. 9: MC in BUT: comparison of RSSI distribution

(see Figure 8) is higher than RSSI for MP №5. Moreover, the difference in signal strength for the two neighbor MPs could be the same (GW11, GW9) or even more (GW15) than for two distant MPs.

Consequently, the gathered dataset is unstable, i.e., measurements taken from the neighboring positions can vary significantly in terms of RSSI values. The following reasons could explain it:

- GWs in this experiment are in a location different from the place of data collection, in a different plane;
- GWs are located just from one side of the parking lot, in contrast to the previous case, when the equipment was evenly distributed over the measurement area (avoiding symmetry). Moreover, even along this one side, there were points relative to which the GWs were concentrated at a fairly close distance, and, conversely, points where the nearest GW was twice as far away;
- The measurement campaign for this case was conducted during working days. In addition, the COVID spot was organized on this parking lot those days. It led to the point that the parking lot environment was constantly changing.

To conclude, the accuracy based on this case may not be entirely correct. However, this dataset can investigate the dependence of the LoRaWAN-based localization accuracy on the spacing between MPs. Looking at Table II we can notice that:

- The increasing of the step between MPs by 2 reduced localization accuracy on average at least by 1.5 (cases *b-c*, and *d-e*);
- The configuration of the MPs, in other words, the amount of the close neighbors, plays a big role: the more the neighbors - the higher is accuracy. Comparing cases *a* (rectangular) and *b* (line), it could be seen that despite the spacing in case *b* is 1 m lower, on average the localization accuracy there is on 1.5 m worse than

in case *a*.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of comparison of different outdoor datasets in terms of parameters (area, number of GWs, amount of MPs, and spacing between them) and best achieved accuracy are represented in Table III. The localization approach used for all cases is k -NN fingerprinting.

TABLE III: Mean Errors

Parameters	Dataset		
	DS in [12]	DS №1	DS №2.1
Area	53 km ²	111 km ²	595 m ²
Number of GWs	72	22	7
Average spacing, m	195	499	3.54
Accuracy (k -NN), m	398	1047	6.42

Overall, more statistical results are needed to derive clear dependencies of the accuracy of LoRaWAN-based localization on the parameters of the dataset. However, for now, it is possible to conclude that the distance between MPs significantly affects the localization accuracy: experiment with Dataset 2 shows that the doubling of the step between MPs reduces the localization accuracy on average by at least 1.5. Secondly, the number of nearest neighbors for each MP plays an important role: MPs located in a line will determine the localization accuracy less than the same number of MP points with the same interval but covering a rectangular area. Finally, when estimating the applicability of the technology based on the published results, one should pay attention to the parameters of the measurement/simulation campaign: 398 m mean error claimed in [12] for the whole city sounds differently and is not the same as 6.42 m mean error for the relatively small outdoor area, which can be handled easier and more carefully, i.e., using a denser coverage of the study area with measurement points.

VI. CONCLUSION

LoRaWAN is a proven communication solution actively used for various monitoring tasks to connect elements of the IIoT world. Due to long-range, sub GHz band, low power consumption, this technology could also be a good candidate for localization purposes for wearable devices involved in industrial scenarios as an energy-efficient supplement for conventional GNSSs. However, a number of works confirm the low accuracy of LoRaWAN-based localization, both indoor and outdoor.

This work investigated two outdoor datasets to identify the possibility of applying LoRaWAN technology as a localization solution. This work aims not to argue with the published results but to estimate the mean error of LoRaWAN-based localization for two particular outdoor datasets, to explore the dependence of localization accuracy on the parameters of the measurement campaign and make

assumptions about the prospects for using this technology for localization in the future.

For the dataset gathered over Brno, Czech Republic, the minimal mean localization error turned out to be 1.04 km, however, this dataset was not collected for localization purposes. The accuracy for the planned dataset covering area 8.5×70 m is 6.42 m that sounds promising in terms of LoRaWAN-based localization.

Comparing the parameters of the different datasets, we demonstrated how significantly the localization accuracy can change depending on the measurement campaign parameters. Also we made a step towards an adequate comparison of the results obtained by researchers for LoRaWAN-based localization for different datasets.

Returning to the question about the prospects of study of LoRaWAN technology as a localization solution, we should point out that 6.42 m accuracy is still a large mean error. However, considering the disadvantages of the conducted measurement campaign and the possibility of increasing the resolution of fingerprinting maps by applying ML-algorithms to improve precision, it can be concluded that LoRaWAN has potential as a localization solution in industrial scenarios that are often represented by relatively small areas.

Future plans envisage a) more detailed studies of the dependence of the localization accuracy achieved using LoRaWAN technology, both on the distance between MPs and on the number of GWs, obtaining more consistent results, and b) investigation of the feasibility of LoRaWAN solution for indoor/outdoor localization.

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